

METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF USING OUR NATIONAL HERITAGE IN RAISING SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS DURING LESSONS

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Abstract. *In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the tasks of creating a national system for evaluating the quality of education were determined in order to raise the natural literacy of pupils to a new level in terms of quality, introduce innovative forms and methods of teaching into the educational process. In this regard, this article is dedicated to methods of using national heritage in raising spiritual and moral qualities of primary school pupils.*

Keywords: *education, upbringing, spiritual, moral, pupils, literacy.*

Today, in Uzbekistan, the educational issues of raising the spiritual and moral qualities of elementary school pupils in the course of lessons are gaining relevance. Because the role of education and upbringing in the use of our national heritage in raising the spiritual and moral qualities of primary school pupils in the course of lessons is great. The adoption of the new version of the Law "On Education" dated September 23, 2020 in our republic is of great importance in the spiritual and moral education in the school education system.

As a result, in our country, education and upbringing using our national heritage in the process of raising the spiritual and moral qualities of elementary school pupils is carried out spontaneously until now. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-5712 dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the tasks of creating a national system for evaluating the quality of education were determined in order to raise the natural literacy of pupils to a new level in terms of quality, introduce innovative forms and methods of teaching into the educational process. Encouraging elementary school pupils to study natural sciences helps them to develop a holistic view of the world, as well as the student realizes that natural sciences, including physics and chemistry, are very interesting subjects, and he/she feels motivated to learn them. Works on providing primary school pupils with scientific and worldly knowledge about the secrets of the world of plants, respecting the environment, forming activities related to its enrichment, protecting and preserving the nature of our country require that they be carried out consistently through educational activities in mutual cooperation with teachers, parents, and the public.

The task of spiritual and moral education and upbringing requires the formation of scientific competencies in the student, acquisition of specific knowledge, skills, standardized by the curriculum of "Social Humanities", "Natural Sciences" and "Natural Education" and unified SES. In accordance with the curriculum, the content of spiritual and moral knowledge has been

expanded by connecting the discipline of "Natural Science" with the mother tongue and reading literacy, and the scientific-theoretical materials were enriched with concrete facts.

In the planning of interdisciplinary lessons in primary school, it is important to form universal educational activities, the ability to evaluate the surrounding world, tasks aimed at stabilizing a healthy lifestyle, environmental safety, spiritual and moral education and upbringing. Lesson is the main form of educational organization. Each student's unique characteristics are taken into account in the lesson, favorable conditions are created for all students to learn the basics of discipline studied in the classroom, to educate and develop their intellectual abilities and spiritual and moral qualities.

Due to the requirement to incorporate innovative education and knowledge into the content of general education subjects, this aspect also requires a unique approach in the integration of subjects. In the natural sciences, this approach covers the environment, the universe and man, and the existence in general. It will be necessary to inculcate a direct connection to nature in the content of mother tongue, mathematics, reading, fine arts and music, to be able to feel the beauty of nature in the presented examples of artistic works, to pay attention to the situations in which the heroes of the work are in the spirit of honoring our national values.

Also, the will to inculcate the essence of these concepts into the content of other sciences helps to fulfill the responsible task of bringing up a strong and mentally healthy person. Among the interdisciplinary integrated courses in the educational process non-traditional types of lessons such as: small lecture, conversation, problem-based lesson, multimedia applications, training trip, creative research, composition, discussion in the practical application of knowledge in the, viewing of our historical-spiritual values, have been organized, which have found their expression in this process. Interdisciplinary integrated classes are defined as an equal combination of knowledge from different educational areas that complement each other. That is, a combination (after drawing, playing games or going for a walk in the open air); in complex lessons, tasks are performed through various types of activities through associative connections between them. In this, one type of activity dominates, and the other complements it, creates an emotional mood; interdisciplinary integrated lessons combine knowledge of different educational areas on an equal basis, complement each other (the concept of "mood" through music, literature, paintings is taken into account).

It should be noted that the method of conducting an integrated lesson differs from the method of conducting a regular lesson. Teaching goals are achieved only when interdisciplinary spiritual-ethical lessons are organized in harmony with students' educational activities and teacher's pedagogical activities. This type of lessons, which discovers a different feature, is lively, attractive, extremely interesting and impressive in terms of content, and differs from other forms of lessons by creating a positive mental and competitive atmosphere in the classroom. Interdisciplinary spiritual-ethical lessons increase the level of interest, expand the student's perception and imagination, increase the possibilities of creativity, communication, personal qualities, observe and make rational decisions. It is important to organize systematic work aimed at interdisciplinary improvement of the culture of raising spiritual and moral qualities of primary school pupils in the course of lessons. Thorough and solid assimilation of the fundamentals of "Natural Science" and "Education" will form pupils' skills, qualifications and competences related to the culture and knowledge of spiritual and moral qualities. It is important for students to follow a healthy lifestyle and develop independence skills.

In the process of experiment, simple, easy and effective methods were chosen for students to master the educational material, which are suitable for the purpose of teaching and can ensure the high reliability of achieving the best results in the organization of interdisciplinary integrative lessons. Independent work, problem statement, heuristic (partial research) methods are effective in forming the culture of raising the moral and ethical qualities of primary school pupils during the lessons. Today, the test results of these methods in the primary education system show the high level of effectiveness of organizing interdisciplinary integrated classes. It serves to form a conscious attitude to the environment through the acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies of interdisciplinary students in science, expansion of their scientific worldview, intellectual development, personal upbringing, improvement of spiritual and moral thinking. It is shown that primary school teachers should acquire special methodological knowledge and skills, have methodical preparation necessary in pedagogical practice in order to successfully apply modern approaches in the interdisciplinary formation of the culture of raising spiritual and moral qualities in primary school pupils.

In particular, in the research work, based on the **culturological (cultural) approach**, the culture of educating the spiritual and moral qualities of elementary school pupils is aimed at interdisciplinary education, opening of their intellectual, cultural, sophistication and moral potential. **The axiological approach** aims to take into account the importance of the formation of the culture of raising spiritual and moral qualities in each pupil in the protection of social life and the environment, as well as the life experience of the pupil in the process of education and upbringing. **The situational (problematic) approach** allows the pupil to acquire not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills and basic life competencies in the process of creating and solving pedagogical situations in the process of organizing training sessions. **The activity-based approach** is directed to the analysis and elimination of teaching problems that have arisen in the classroom and extracurricular activities organized during the experimental process.

In the course of research, in the process of forming the culture of raising the spiritual and moral qualities of elementary school pupils, the content of interdisciplinary topics, handouts allowing the application of cultural, axiological, situational (problematic), activity-based modern methodological approaches, will be known. From the point of view of their spiritual and moral qualities, pupils are developed the skills, abilities and competences of forming a high level of interest in educational activities, independently completing educational tasks.

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